

CONTRIBUTION OF INDIVIDUAL FINANCIAL INSTRUMENTS FOR BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION, IMPROVEMENT OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES AND PROTECTION OF HABITATS AND LANDSCAPE IN THE BULGARIAN AGRICULTURAL SECTOR

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Abstract

The aim of the paper is to estimate the contribution of CAP on improvement of ecosystem services and protection of habitats and landscape in the Bulgarian agricultural sector. It can be concluded that the most important financial instruments in phase 1 and phase 2 of the CAP to achieve the objective - protecting biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape in the sector are: Measure 211, Measure 13 and Measure 11.

Keywords: CAP, ecosystem services, landscape, habitats, agriculture

Abstrakt

Ziel des Papiers ist es, den Beitrag der GAP zur Verbesserung der Ökosystemleistungen und zum Schutz von Lebensräumen und Landschaft im bulgarischen Agrarsektor abzuschätzen. Es kann festgestellt werden, dass die wichtigsten Finanzinstrumente in Phase 1 und Phase 2 der GAP zur Erreichung des Ziels - Schutz der Biodiversität, Verbesserung der Ökosystemleistungen und Erhaltung von Lebensräumen und Landschaft in diesem Sektor - sind: Maßnahme 211, Maßnahme 13 und Maßnahme 11.

Schlüsselwörter: GAP, Ökosystemleistungen, Landschaft, Lebensräume, Landwirtschaft

Résumé

L'objectif de ce document est d'estimer la contribution de la PAC à l'amélioration des services écosystémiques et à la protection des habitats et des paysages dans le secteur agricole bulgare. On peut conclure que les instruments financiers les plus importants des phases 1 et 2 de la PAC pour atteindre l'objectif - protéger la biodiversité, améliorer les services écosystémiques et conserver les habitats et les paysages dans le secteur sont Mesure 211, Mesure 13 et Mesure 11.

Mots-clés: PAC, services écosystémiques, paysage, habitats, agriculture

Introduction

Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is one of the greatest part of the EU from financial point of view and affects 8.7 million farmers (Borisov, Kolaj and Yanceva, 2019). Therefore it earns much attention, several researchers are dealing with this issue. Besides the continuous communications and analyses of the European Commission (EC, 2003, 2008, 2009, 2011, 2013, 2017) which evaluates the efficiency of the financial instruments for support, (Ackrill, 2000) and (Burell and Oskam, 2000) gave a detailed overview of the first couple of decades of the CAP. Swinnen has published many books and articles on different aspects of the CAP, assessed the previous reforms (Swinnen, 2008), the future of the direct

payments (Swinnen, 2009) or its impacts on ecosystem services, protection of habitats and landscape in member states.

The aim of the paper is to estimate the contribution of CAP on improvement of ecosystem services and protection of habitats and landscape in the Bulgarian agricultural sector.

Financial assistance for the protection of biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape is carried out using two approaches (post intervention) within the frame of CAP (Borisov, P., Radev and Nikolov, 2014). Financial instruments that are set for action aimed to set a framework for the sector to ensure that objective.

The first approach under the CAP emphasizes protection of biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape by applying a scheme of direct payments per hectare. The second approach (pillar) is the use of financial schemes to promote investment activity in the sector for the implementation of practices that can improve ecosystem services and to protect habitats and landscape affected by activities in the agricultural sector. The second approach involves Rural Development Program (RDP), in which a specific financial instrument are set up to achieve the intended goals. In Table 1 are given the intervention tools within the CAP - 2007-2013

Table 1. Tools to support the agricultural sector to protect biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape /active in the period 2014-2018/. Source: Own survey, 2019

Tools	CAP - pillar 1 and pillar 2	CAP - Pillar 2
Specific actions for protection of biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape	(1) Payments to farmers for environmental constraints in mountain areas - (Measure 211, RDP 2007-2013, which is part of Pillar 2 of the CAP) (2) Payments to farmers in areas with handicaps, other than mountain areas - (Measure 212, RDP 2007-2013) (4) (Measure 213 of RDP 2007-2013) (3) Measure 10 (RDP 2014-2020) (4) Measure 11 (RDP 2014-2020) (5) Measure 12 (RDP 2014-2020) (6) Measure 13 (RDP 2014-2020) (7) Measure 14 (RDP 2014-2020)	(1) Specific sub-program of RDP 2014-2020

In the first and second phase of the CAP have the following six (6) financial mechanisms to support the agricultural sector to achieve protection of biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape:

(1) Payments to farmers for environmental constraints in mountain areas - (measure 211, PRD - 2007-2013)

(2) Payments to farmers in areas with handicaps, other than mountain areas - (measure 212, RDP - 2007-2013)

(3) Natura 2000 payments (measure 211, RPD 2007-2013)

(4) Measure 10 (RDP 2014-2020)

(5) Measure 11 (RDP 2014-2020)

(6) Measure 12 (RDP 2014-2020)

(7) Measure 13 (RDP 2014-2020)

(8) Measure 14 (RDP 2014-2020)

RDP 2007-2013, the measures that can be defined as specific and fully intended to protect biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape are measure 211, measures 212 and measure 213. In subsequent RDP 2014-2020 measures specifically designed to protect biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape are: measure 10, measure 11 and measure 12 (first pillar for intervention of CAP) and thematic sub-program RDP 2014-2020.

Figure 1 contains information on the allocation of financial assistance for achieving the objective - protecting biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape. Clearly stands out the contribution of measure 211 "Payments to farmers for environmental constraints for mountain areas" to achieve the objective. Under this measure, farms received 231 561.2 thousand BGN financial assistance. Under the measure 211 received respectively and most applications for financial assistance - 219 644 applications, 99% of them were approved and allowed to contract for financial support.

Under Measure 212 "Payments to farmers for environmental constraints in mountain areas", utilized financial resources amounted to 100 444.67. thousand BGN under measure 212 received a total of 89 610 applications for financial assistance. Of those 89 610 applications have been approved 99.5% and allowed to contract for financial assistance.

Figure 1. Payments under the measures 211, 212 and 213 of the RDP 2007-2013. Source: Data of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry - Sofia.

Under Measure 213 "Natura 2000 payments" received a total of 2427 number of applications that have been approved 2071. This measure, which is the smallest contribution in the utilization of financial assistance are payments amounting to 97 147, 31 thousand BGN. Measure 213 is the main financial instrument for financial support for establishments covered areas "Natura 2000". Bulgaria has identified 233 protected areas "Natura 2000" in accordance with the Habitats Directive (Sites of Community / SCI). Certain are 119 protected areas "Natura 2000" in accordance with the Birds Directive (Special Protection Areas / SPA). SCI and SPAs cover 41 053,2 km² of the territory of Bulgaria, of which 38 are 231,84 km² onshore and 2 821,35 km² belong to the maritime territory. Network "Natura 2000" in Bulgaria includes 90 habitat types and 121 species other than birds - including 28 priority habitats and 8 priority species and 120 birds and 70 migratory birds. The land part of "Natura 2000" for the birds is almost complete.

Figure 2 contains information on the amounts paid by individual measures (M10, M11, M12, M13 and M14) covered in the first pillar of the CAP (2014-2020). With the most important intervention in the sector (direct payments per hectare) stands measure 13 "Payments to areas facing natural or other specific constraints". Under this measure are paid 268 966 thousand BGN, which is 38% of total disbursements under the 5 above mentioned measures. With almost equal contribution to achieving the objectives are M10 and M11. In M10, the paid funds are 145 520 thousand BGN, and M11 - 145 970 thousand BGN. The lowest contribution stands M14, namely under this measure are paid 3 885 thousand BGN (this measure is intended for forestry, where the majority of beneficiaries are state structures)

Figure 2. Paid financial assistance (in 000 BGN) under the various measures of the first pillar (phase 2014-2020) to support the agricultural sector. Source: Data of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry - Sofia.

In measure 10 of the first pillar of the CAP from 2014 to 2020 are covered six (6) lines of intervention for achieving the objectives. Figure 3 contains information about the number of received and approved applications for assistance in these six areas.

Figure 3. Number of applications approved and authorized for payment within the measure 10. Source: Data of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry - Sofia.

The data show that the greatest interest of farmers are in two areas: (1) Soil erosion control and (2) The protection of endangered local varieties important for agriculture. In the first direction are applied 4920 applications, 4729 of which have received authorization for payment to the applicant. The second direction were applied 3890 applications, of which 3844 applications were approved for funding. With the slightest interest among farmers are determined direction "Traditional practices for seasonal grazing." Within this strand of measure 10 received only 1017 applications, of which 993 were approved.

Although it has the greatest interest in the directions "Soil erosion control" and "Conservation of endangered local varieties for farming," according to data of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry the number of submitted and approved applications, the highest rate of assisted areas within M10 is achieved by direction "Maintenance of habitats of protected species in arable land with ornithological importance." Within this area, the aided area amounted to 330 865 thousand ha (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Size assisted area under measure 10 (on separate sub-measures). Source: Data of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry - Sofia.

Figure 5 provides information on the amounts paid in different directions enshrined in measure 10. According to the criterion - paid financial assistance largest contribution in the use of M10 has a direction "Keeping the habitat of protected species in arable land with ornithological importance." Within this direction were paid 48 321 thousand. Lev farmers. Also significant contribution stands and direction "Control of soil erosion" of money amounting to 35 822 thousand. Lev.

Figure 5. Paid financial assistance (in 000 BGN) for each sub-measure within measure 10. Source: Data of Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry - Sofia.

Conclusions

It can be concluded that the most important financial instruments in phase 1 and phase 2 of the CAP to achieve the objective - protecting biodiversity, improve ecosystem services and conservation of habitats and landscape in the sector are:

- Measure 211 "Payments to farmers for environmental constraints for mountain areas" to achieve the objective. Under this measure, farms received 231 561.2 thousand. Lev financial assistance, this measure received respectively and most applications for financial assistance - 219 644 applications, 99% of them have been approved;

- Measure 13 "Payments to areas facing natural or other specific constraints". Under this measure are paid 268 966 thousand BGN, which is 38% of total disbursements under the 5 specific measures (m 10, M11, M12, M13, M14) in the RDP 2014-2020;

- Measure 11 is the second most important measure under the first pillar of the CAP from 2014 to 2020. By this measure are utilized most funds after measure 13. The main financial contribution is implemented through sub-measure 11.1 "Payments for conversion to organic farming";

- Measure 10. The largest contribution to the implementation of the measure is the direction "" Keeping the habitat of protected species in arable land with ornithological importance."

References

Ackrill, R. (2000) Common Agricultural Policy. Contemporary European Studies 9, Sheffi eld Academic Press, p. 244.

Borisov, P., R. Kolaj, S. Yancheva, C. Yancheva (2019). Influence of common agriculture policy on Bulgarian agriculture. Bulgarian Journal of Agricultural Science, 2019 vol. 25 (No.3), 439-447 pp.

Borisov, P., Radev T. & Nikolov, D., (2014). Analysis of the strategic factors for the development of small agricultural farms in Bulgaria, Economics and Management of Agriculture, 2

Burell, A. & Oskam, A. eds. (2000): Agricultural policy and enlargement of the European Union. Wageningen Pers., Wageningen, The Netherlands, pp. 53-68.

EC (2003) Council Regulation No. 1782/2003 of 29 September 2003 establishing common rules for direct support schemes under the common agricultural policy and establishing certain support schemes for farmers.

EC (2008) Commission Regulation No. 1242/2008 of 8 December 2008 establishing a Community typology for agricultural holdings.

EC (2009a) Council Regulation No. 73/2009 of 19 January 2009 establishing common rules for direct support schemes for farmers under the common agricultural policy and establishing certain support schemes for farmers.

EC (2009b) Health Check" of the Common Agricultural Policy. http://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/healthcheck/index_en.htm

EC (2011a) Common Agricultural Policy towards 2020. Commission Staff Working Paper, SEC(2011) 1153, Brussels, Belgium.

EC (2011b) Average direct payments per hectare for the year 2017 – existing legislation – data to use. 12734/11, Brussels, Belgium.

EC (2013) European Parliament and of the Council Regulation No. 1307/2013 of 17 December 2013 establishing rules for direct payments to farmers under support schemes within the framework of the common agricultural policy and repealing Council Regulation No. 637/2008 and No. 73/2009.

EC (2017a): Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. The Future of Food and Farming. COM(2017) 713 final, Brussels, Belgium.

EC (2017b): Report on the distribution of direct payments to agricultural producers (financial year 2016). Ref. Ares (2017)5942828, Brussels, Belgium.

MAF (2010) Preliminary Data Census for Bulgarian farmers for 2010, published by MAF.

MAF (2013) Agriculture in Bulgaria, published by MAF.

Swinnen, J. F. M. (2009) On the Future of Direct Payments. Paper presented at the BEPA Workshop. February 26, 2009, European Commission, Brussels.

Swinnen, J. F. M. ed. (2008) The Perfect Storm: The Political Economy of the Fischler Reforms of the Common Agricultural Policy, CEPS, Brussels, p. 192.